

TELEVISION AS AN ENTERTAINMENT INDUSTRY.

Toshqinboyeva Shohsanam Oybekovna

Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

Foreign language and literature: English 105 group student

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Abstract: Nowadays, we cannot imagine our daily life without a mirror. This article provides information about the influence of television on the human psyche, the order of broadcasting and entertainment TV programs.

Key words: Television, telereport, teleminiature, video information, telecomposition.

Television activity is carried out on the basis of the norms of telejournalism. Telejournalism is a combination of the rules of journalism with the possibilities of television. Genres of telejournalism also arise from the combination of press genres and television features. Informative, analytical and art-journalistic genres of the press, combined with the features of television, turn into telecasts, telereports, telefilms, telechats, telereports, telecommentaries, teleessays, telefeuilletons and others. A collection of TV shows dedicated to a certain topic is called a TV magazine. At the same time, television is a special type of mass media. In performing its function, it uses not only journalism, but also the art of speech, literature, theater, cinema, and music. That is why television ranks high among other mass media. Telenovela, teleminiature, telefilm, teleplay, telecomposition and other genres common to literature and art are also used as a result of wide use of such types of art in TV shows.

The variety of television programs of Uzbekistan Television provides an opportunity to cover and interestingly reflect all spheres of social, political, economic, industrial, cultural and spiritual life of the republic.

Television (Greek: $\tau\acute{\epsilon}\lambda\epsilon$ - far and Latin: video - see) is a system of remote transmission of moving images and sound. The working principle of television is based on dividing the image frame into lines. The frame rate is selected depending on the image change rate. Television, the field of science, technology and culture related to the transmission of visible information (moving images) over a certain distance using radio-electronic means; one of the means of information dissemination. Mankind has always been busy with the desire to see things and events far away from the place where he lives. This desire is reflected in the legends and tales of many peoples. For example, Alisher Navoi expressed this desire in an artistic form in the epic "Farhod and Shirin" (the Chinese Farhod falls in love with an Armenian girl after seeing Shirin's beauty in the mirror). This desire of the people was mainly realized in the 20th century, when

electronics became a "magic mirror" ("mirror world"). Television is based on the principle of sequential transmission of image elements (advanced at the end of the 19th century by the Portuguese scientist A. di Paiva and independently by the Russian scientist P. I. Bakhmetov). Until the 30s of the 20th century, optical-mechanical devices were used in the analysis and synthesis of images (the German engineer P.G. Nipkov started their development in 1884). The first electronic television system appeared in the mid-1930s. Since the human eye is the last link that receives transmitted television images, television systems are built taking into account the eye's vision processes, that is, television is based on the characteristics of the eye. Photocells were used instead of flasks and sticks. If the image of an object is captured through a lens on a panel consisting of photo elements, electrical signals proportional to the intensity of the light coming from individual elements of the image are obtained.

Television images are transmitted in 3 processes:

1. Converting light emitted or reflected by a transmitting object into electrical signals;
2. Transmission and reception of electrical signals through communication channels;
3. Conversion of electrical signals into light pulses that form an optical image of the object. The process of successive conversion of image elements into electrical signals during transmission, and of transmitted signals into image elements during reception, is called image restoration. Image analysis and synthesis processes should be synchronous and syntactic. The linearizer is widely adopted in the television broadcasting system; the resulting image frame will have a horizontal line structure. A sync pulse is transmitted at the end of each line and frame to maintain the synchronization of playback. In this way, the television stya controls the restoration of all televisions in its area of influence. The processes of creating and restoring optical images in television are technically mainly carried out using a vacuum electron beam tube.

Among the transmitting tubes, the internal photoeffect vidicon and the external photoeffect superorthicon, and from the receiving tubes various kinescopes are common. In black-and-white television, the light signal (video signal) is amplified and converted into an electrical signal as it exits the transmission tube. In this case, a radio channel or a cable channel serves as a communication channel. At the receiver, the received signals are converted into light rays in a single-beam kinescope; in which the kinescope screen is covered with a phosphor that emits white light.

Because color television can reproduce all natural colors optically from the 3 primary colors—red, green, and blue—taken in certain proportions, a television transmission camera uses not one, but 3 tubes to generate the illuminance signal and the primary color signals. All these signals are coded during transmission (telecenter), and decoded during reception (television receiver). Since the mid-80s, work on the digital television system has been carried out and put into practice. In this system, a sequence of coded (numbered) combinations of electrical pulses is used. A cable television system is also being used. It will have no atmosphere or other interference. Cables (light conductors) are mainly laid underground.

Television systems are classified according to the following main features: according to the quality feature - white (monochrome), color, stereomonochrome and stereocolor; according to how it forms signals (video information) — analog and discrete (digital); according to the frequency of the spectrum of the communication channel - broadband and narrowband.

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